

Overview of Hygrothermally Stable Laminates with Improved Extension-twist Coupling

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SUMMARY

Material-independent necessary and sufficient conditions for hygrothermal curvature stability of laminated composite plates have been derived. Hygrothermally stable asymmetric solutions exist for laminates of five or more plies. These solutions have been optimized for maximum extension-twist coupling, constructed, and tested to demonstrate improved coupling properties.

Keywords: hygrothermal stability, extension-twist coupling, elastic tailoring, classical lamination theory, design and testing

INTRODUCTION

Coupling of deformation modes can be used advantageously to elastically tailor the response of a composite structure. For example, extension-twist coupling has applications ranging from wind turbine blades to tilt-rotor aircraft. Other types of coupling include extension-bending, bending-twist, and anticlastic coupling. Extension-twist coupling is only achievable using asymmetric stacking sequences, which often produce hygrothermal instabilities, meaning that temperature or moisture changes cause bending or warping [1]. Past design methods involve obtaining the desired coupling properties then attempting to minimize hygrothermal effects [2]. The present work takes hygrothermal stability as the primary constraint then investigates the achievable elastic properties.

The first established family of extension-twist-coupled composites that retain hygrothermal stability was detailed by Winckler [3] and given by the stacking sequence

$$[\theta / (\theta-90)_2 / \theta / -\theta / (90-\theta)_2 / -\theta]. \quad (1)$$

These Winckler-type laminates have been the industry standard since their introduction. A review of their usage has been published previously [4]. It has been discovered, however, that this family does not contain all hygrothermally stable laminates. Further, it has also been found that Winckler's family does not maximize extension-twist

coupling among laminates consisting of eight plies. This work first provides an overview of how hygrothermal stability is enforced as given in previous work [5]. Then it presents solutions and verification to maximized extension-twist coupling.

HYGROTHERMAL STABILITY CONDITIONS

As given in classical lamination theory [6] for a laminate made of specially orthotropic plies, the non-mechanical in-plane forces and shears and out-of-plane moments and curvatures are related to the in-plane strains and out-of-plane curvatures as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_{xx} \\ N_{yy} \\ N_{xy} \\ M_{xx} \\ M_{yy} \\ M_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}^{(T,H)} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} & B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & A_{26} & B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} \\ A_{16} & A_{26} & A_{66} & B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} \\ \hline B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} & D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{16} \\ B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} & D_{12} & D_{22} & D_{26} \\ B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} & D_{16} & D_{26} & D_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx} \\ \varepsilon_{yy} \\ \gamma_{xy} \\ \kappa_{xx} \\ \kappa_{yy} \\ \kappa_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where A_{ij} , B_{ij} , and D_{ij} are the in-plane and coupling stiffness coefficients respectively and $()^{(T,H)}$ indicates non-mechanical quantities. Since hygrothermal stability can be defined as having the out-of-plane curvatures equal to zero for any change in temperature or moisture, this can be expressed as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_{xx} \\ N_{yy} \\ N_{xy} \\ M_{xx} \\ M_{yy} \\ M_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}^{(T,H)} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & A_{26} \\ A_{16} & A_{26} & A_{66} \\ \hline B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} \\ B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} \\ B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx} \\ \varepsilon_{yy} \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

The non-mechanical in-plane forces and shears and out-of-plane moments and curvatures for an n -ply laminate are given by

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_{xx} \\ N_{yy} \\ N_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}^{(T,H)} = T_2 \begin{Bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} + T_3 \sum_{k=1}^n \begin{Bmatrix} \cos 2\theta_k \\ -\cos 2\theta_k \\ \sin 2\theta_k \end{Bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} M_{xx} \\ M_{yy} \\ M_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}^{(T,H)} = T_1 \sum_{k=1}^n \begin{Bmatrix} \cos 2\theta_k \\ -\cos 2\theta_k \\ \sin 2\theta_k \end{Bmatrix} (2k - n - 1) \quad (4)$$

where θ_k is the angle of the k^{th} ply, and T_1 , T_2 , and T_3 are solely functions of the material properties and temperature and moisture changes.

Using (2), it can be proven that the necessary and sufficient conditions to ensure hygrothermal stability are either [5]

$$N_{xx}^{(T,H)}=N_{yy}^{(T,H)} \text{ and } N_{xy}^{(T,H)}=M_{xx}^{(T,H)}=M_{yy}^{(T,H)}=M_{xy}^{(T,H)}=0$$

or

(5a, b)

$$B_{ij}=0.$$

Since the latter precludes extension-twist coupling, the former condition is of primary interest to this work. It should be noted that when the conditions are replaced into (4), all the material-dependent parameters cancel, making the conditions material independent. Asymmetric stacking sequences that retain hygrothermal stability were found for families of laminates consisting of five or more plies. A sensitivity analysis performed in previous work demonstrated that small perturbations in ply angle (typical of hand-layup error) did not affect the out-of-plane stability of hygrothermally stable asymmetric laminates any more than it would affect symmetric laminates [5]. Finite element models and manufacturing of representative laminates verified the hygrothermal stability.

OPTIMIZATION OF EXTENSION-TWIST COUPLING

As given in Classical Lamination Theory, the relationship between force and moment resultants and the mid-plane strains and curvatures are expressed as [6]

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_{xx} \\ N_{yy} \\ N_{xy} \\ M_{xx} \\ M_{yy} \\ M_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} & B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & A_{26} & B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} \\ A_{16} & A_{26} & A_{66} & B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} \\ B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} & D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{16} \\ B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} & D_{12} & D_{22} & D_{26} \\ B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} & D_{16} & D_{26} & D_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx} \\ \varepsilon_{yy} \\ \gamma_{xy} \\ \kappa_{xx} \\ \kappa_{yy} \\ \kappa_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{Bmatrix} N_{xx} \\ N_{yy} \\ N_{xy} \\ M_{xx} \\ M_{yy} \\ M_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}^{(T,H)}. \quad (6)$$

where all parameters are as given before. The mid-plane strains and curvatures may then be calculated as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx} \\ \varepsilon_{yy} \\ \gamma_{xy} \\ \kappa_{xx} \\ \kappa_{yy} \\ \kappa_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_{11} & \alpha_{12} & \alpha_{16} & \beta_{11} & \beta_{12} & \beta_{16} \\ \alpha_{12} & \alpha_{22} & \alpha_{26} & \beta_{21} & \beta_{22} & \beta_{26} \\ \alpha_{16} & \alpha_{26} & \alpha_{66} & \beta_{61} & \beta_{62} & \beta_{66} \\ \beta_{11} & \beta_{21} & \beta_{61} & \delta_{11} & \delta_{12} & \delta_{16} \\ \beta_{12} & \beta_{22} & \beta_{62} & \delta_{12} & \delta_{22} & \delta_{26} \\ \beta_{16} & \beta_{26} & \beta_{66} & \delta_{16} & \delta_{26} & \delta_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} N_{xx} \\ N_{yy} \\ N_{xy} \\ M_{xx} \\ M_{yy} \\ M_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx} \\ \varepsilon_{yy} \\ \gamma_{xy} \\ \kappa_{xx} \\ \kappa_{yy} \\ \kappa_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}^{(T,H)}. \quad (7)$$

For an axial load in the x-direction, the twist curvature can be expressed as

$$\kappa_{xy} = \beta_{16} N_{xx} + \kappa_{xy}^{(T,H)}. \quad (8)$$

Therefore, β_{16} is the parameter that governs extension-twist coupling. A non-dimensional performance parameter can then be expressed as

$$\eta = |ntLE_{11}\beta_{16}| \quad (9)$$

where n is the number of plies, t is the lamina thickness, L is the specimen length, and E_{11} is the material modulus of elasticity along the fiber direction.

Within the constraints of the hygrothermal stability conditions, an optimizer was used to identify stacking sequences for which extension-twist coupling is maximized for each of five, six, eight, and ten plies. Also included for comparison is an optimized Winckler-type laminate. Extension-twist coupling is material dependent, and a T300/976 graphite/epoxy material system was chosen; its properties are given in Table I. The optimizer uses sequential quadratic programming implementation in conjunction with the conditions in (5a) and random seed angles to arrive at an extremal value of the β_{16} for a given number of plies. Table II lists the optimization results for each laminate along with the performance parameter.

Table I. Material Properties of T300/976.

E_{11}	125 GPa
E_{22}	8.45 GPa
G_{12}	4.3 GPa
N_{12}	0.328
Thickness	0.152 mm

Table II. Optimization results.

Laminate	Optimal Stacking Sequence (deg.)	η
5-ply	[-58.7/11.4/45/78.6/-31.3]	3449
6-ply	[21.2/-63.8/-48.7/48.7/63.8/-21.2]	3787
8-ply	[21.5/-72.1/-57.9/29.6/-29.6/57.9/72.1/-21.5]	2471
10-ply	[16.2/-69.0/-65.3/31.8/42.1/-42.1/-31.8/65.3/69.0/-16.2]	2453
Winckler	[22.5/-67.5 ₂ /22.5/-22.5/67.5 ₂ /-22.5]	2080

EXTENSION-TWIST EXPERIMENTAL VERIFICATION

All five laminates in Table II were constructed from a preimpregnated T300/976 graphite/epoxy material system with properties given in Table I. Each ply was hand cut, laid up in a flat aluminium mold, and cured in an autoclave with a cure cycle given in Figure 1. Cured laminates were confirmed to be hygrothermally stable by fixing three corners and measuring the displacement of the fourth corner. This value was shown to be the same for both anti-symmetric layups and their symmetric counterparts. For example, [21.2/-63.8/-48.7/-48.7/-63.8/21.2] is the symmetric counterpart of the six-ply extension-twist-optimized laminate. Since symmetric layups are known to be hygrothermally stable, warping in these laminates are a quantitative measure of manufacturing imperfections.

Figure 1. Curing Cycle for Graphite/Epoxy Material.

Each laminate was cut into five specimens of approximately 2.54 cm by 17.78 cm (1.0" by 7.0") and tested in an Instron 8874 biaxial tension-torsion machine. Specimens were taken from the center of each laminate to reduce the edge effects. Errors in the cutting process caused one specimen to be discarded from each of the six- and ten-ply laminates. After each specimen was installed in the machine, the tip twist under no axial load, termed pretwist, was recorded. Then, a load increment was applied, and, because of the specimens' low torsion stiffness, the tip was rotated manually until the machine torque indicated a zero value. The load was applied in increments of 445 N (100 lb) up to 2225 N (500 lb). Figure 2 shows a specimen undergoing testing.

The recorded data are plotted in Figures 3 through 6 for the six-ply, eight-ply, ten-ply, and Winckler-type laminate, respectively. The test data from each specimen is referred to in each figure as 'Experimental 1', 'Experimental 2', etc. Initial pretwist values resulting from imperfections in the manufacturing process account for non-zero twists at no loading. Also included on each plot is a non-linear model prediction for extension-twist developed by Armanios *et al* [7] expressed as

$$F_a = \frac{\left(b_1 + \frac{4}{3} b_2 \varphi_{oL} + 2b_3 \varphi_{oL}^2 \right) \varphi_L}{[b_4 - (\varphi_L + \varphi_{oL})]} \quad (10)$$

where F_a is axial force, φ_{oL} is the tip pre-twist angle, φ_L is the tip twist angle, and b_1 - b_4 are functions of the in-plane, A_{ij} , coupling, B_{ij} , and bending, D_{ij} , [7] stiffness coefficients, respectively. The non-linear model is only valid for antisymmetric stacking sequences, and therefore the five-ply laminate is not included in these results. There is good correlation between the experimental data and the model for all laminates.

Figures 7 and 8 plot averaged test data along with maximum and minimum range overlaid with the non-linear model for all four laminates to illustrate the improved coupling properties of the new classes. The abscissa in Figure 7 is the axial force and shows that all new laminates surpass the Winckler-type laminate. Further, laminates with fewer plies have more coupling; this can be explained when considering the lower torsional stiffness of a thinner laminate. Table III gives the percent increase in coupling of each laminate over the Winckler-type laminate. The abscissa in Figure 8 is axial stress, determined by dividing the axial force by the cross-sectional area of the laminate. Again, all new laminates outperform the Winckler-type laminate; however, the ten-ply laminate outperforms the eight-ply laminate. Table IV gives the percent increase in coupling of each laminate over the Winckler-type laminate for this case.

A Monte Carlo simulation was performed to analyze the robustness of extension-twist coupling to small errors in ply angle typically found in hand-layup manufacturing. The six-ply optimized extension-twist laminate was chosen as representative, and the ply angles were varied in a uniform distribution on the interval $\theta_k \pm 2^\circ$, typical of errors seen in hand-lay-up manufacturing. A set of 10^6 samples were taken, β_{16} was calculated, and the error was calculated. Figure 9 plots the distribution of the error for all samples. The reduction in coupling of perturbed laminates was bounded by 10% of its original coupling ability.

Figure 2. A Specimen Undergoing Testing in an Instron Biaxial Tension-Torsion Machine.

Figure 3. Maximized Extension-Twist Coupling of Six-Ply Laminate

Figure 4. Maximized Extension-Twist Coupling of Eight-Ply Laminate

Figure 5. Maximized Extension-Twist Coupling of Ten-Ply Laminate

Figure 6. Maximized Extension-Twist Coupling of a Winckler Laminate

Figure 7. Comparison of Averaged Extension-Twist Coupling for All Laminates

Figure 8. Comparison of Averaged Extension-Twist Coupling for All Laminates

Table III. Improvement over Winckler-Type Laminates when Compared at the Same Force.

Axial Load (lb)	6-ply	8-ply	10-ply
100	119.0%	28.9%	6.3%
200	93.3%	30.1%	12.4%
300	76.0%	29.7%	17.2%
400	65.6%	30.0%	21.6%
500	59.3%	30.2%	25.9%
Average	82.6%	29.8%	16.7%

Table IV. Improvement over Winckler-Type Laminates when Compared at the Same Stress.

Axial Stress (MPa)	6-ply	8-ply	10-ply
100	52.4%	22.0%	20.8%
200	52.2%	22.1%	28.8%
300	48.8%	21.6%	29.9%
400	41.1%	21.2%	30.7%
500	38.2%	29.0%	20.7%
Average	46.5%	23.2%	26.2%

Figure 9. Histogram of Error Based on Uniform Ply-Angle Perturbation

CONCLUSIONS

Necessary and sufficient conditions for hygrothermal stability have been derived, with an overview provided in this work. The conditions can be summarized as either having the coupling stiffness matrix equal to zero or the out-of-plane moments and in-plane shear force equal to zero along with both in-plane axial forces equal to each other. From within these conditions, stacking sequences that maximize extension-twist coupling have been found for laminates consisting of five, six, eight, and ten plies. The six-, eight-, and ten-ply laminates have been constructed and tested to demonstrate their improved coupling properties over the previously-known Winckler-type laminates. When compared at the same axial force level, the best laminate, the six-ply laminate, outperforms the Winckler-type laminate by an average of 83%. When compared at the same stress level, the improvement averages 46%. An investigation of the benefits of the hygrothermal stability conditions on other types of couplings is underway.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge the support given by the National Defense Science and Engineering Graduate Fellowship and the University of Texas System STARS Program.

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